

TEACHER EDUCATION IN THE POST-PANDEMIC PERIOD: IMPACTS OF DISTANCE EDUCATION ON THE WORLD EDUCATION SYSTEM AND NEW REALITIES**Majidov M.***Associate Professor**Agjabadi Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Azerbaijan***Rzayeva G.***Senior Lecturer**Agjabadi Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought about serious changes in the global education system, necessitating a rethinking of the nature of the teacher training process. The rapid transition of traditional classroom activities to an online environment has led to the formulation of new strategies by both students and higher education institutions engaged in teacher training. This period has proven the importance of distance learning opportunities, as well as teachers' digital skills, and has created an important experience base for continuous improvement in the post-pandemic phase.

The crisis situation that arose in the world education system during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially the prolonged closure of schools and the extraordinary transition to a distance (distance) mode of education, led to a rapid transformation of the teaching profession and teacher training systems.

The article analyzes the effects of distance education on teacher training in the post-pandemic period, the main challenges encountered, and new realities, and indicates the importance of redesigning teachers' digital competencies, pedagogical approaches, and professional development mechanisms, referring to international reports and recent studies.

The aim of the article is to systematically examine these changes and formulate practical recommendations for teacher training.

Keywords: post-pandemic, teacher training, distance learning, professional development, digital skills, inclusion.

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education systems globally in 2020–2022. More than 1.6 billion students were left without education, and the most vulnerable family groups in many countries around the world were hit the hardest. This rapid transition forced teachers to urgently teach remotely, and in this process, the shortcomings of teacher training systems inevitably became apparent. Despite the reopening of schools in the post-pandemic period, the experience of distance learning and the new pedagogical and technological needs it created permanently changed the requirements of the teaching profession.

During that period, teacher training programs were organized through online platforms in a short time. Universities began to widely use platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, Microsoft Teams and Zoom. This process provided students with practical knowledge in digital pedagogy, online lesson design and virtual classroom management.

In order to prevent monotony in online classes, applications such as Kahoot, Padlet, Mentimeter began to be widely used in international practice. These tools have created a great opportunity to adapt interactive methods in teacher training programs to the virtual environment.

As psychological tension among students increased during the pandemic, higher education institutions organized seminars on psychological support, stress management, and the development of self-regulation skills. It can be said that this factor increased the importance of the social-emotional learning (SEL) component in teacher training.

The normative framework for organizing distance learning in Azerbaijani higher education institutions was rapidly improved. ADPU, UNEC, BSU, and other higher education institutions implemented online practice models for teacher training, and training packages were developed to improve teachers' digital skills. The Ministry of Education's "Virtual School" platform created an additional practice environment for teacher candidates.

In the post-pandemic stage, the most effective model is considered to be a combination of classroom and distance learning. If we focus on the advantages of hybrid learning, we will see that teaching in this format both increases flexibility and provides future teachers with the ability to operate in various teaching environments.

During the pandemic, the world's education system adopted the term "emergency remote teaching" and this approach was characterized as an unplanned forced measure. The World Bank and other international organizations have drawn lessons from this experience and put forward consistent principles and strategies for the future for long-term results. For example, World Bank analyses show that when the availability of technology and content is not matched by the teacher's ability to teach remotely, the results are not favorable (1, p.17).

OECD and other reports on the world's education system note that the pandemic has accelerated digital education innovations. However, this transformation requires continuous professional development of teachers, online education and necessary investment in technological infrastructure.

Digital learning does not end with the rapid development of technology alone - it calls for teachers to acquire pedagogical skills in this area, use new teaching methods and tools, alternative assessment mechanisms and develop students' knowledge, skills and habits through modern technologies.

UNICEF, UNESCO and other organizations emphasize that distance education can exacerbate existing educational inequalities, especially in areas with limited infrastructure, devices and access to the Internet. This context requires the inclusion of socio-cultural sensitivity and alternative teaching strategies in teacher training.

The pandemic situation has required teachers to integrate technology into lesson design, which has required teachers not only to master the use of platforms, but also to develop new pedagogical skills for online lesson structures, interactive activities and assessment. OECD reports show that successful countries in this area have strengthened targeted professional development programs, online teacher communities and resource sharing (2).

As a result of the pandemic, traditional training (short workshops, seminar-sessions) has expanded to online platforms and new models such as micro-learning and virtual mentoring have begun to be implemented. In their studies, the World Bank and UNESCO note that such models provide more flexible and sustainable professional development opportunities.

Distance learning activities have for some time been a source of both professional and personal stress for teachers (until they adapt to the current conditions). Technical problems, family responsibilities and reduced physical contact with learners have affected the psychosocial well-being of teachers. This has made it necessary to include emotional intelligence and stress management skills in teacher training programs (3).

One of the biggest challenges in distance education is the issue of assessment validity and fairness. Online assessment, formative monitoring and data-based interventions have created new demands for teachers.

Research shows that teacher training programs should serve the purpose of ensuring continuity of education at any point in time, in accordance with the realities of the times, and systematize content on online lesson planning, hybrid pedagogy, virtual assessment and the skillful use of digital tools. This should be reflected consistently throughout the entire program, not just at the level of a single course.

Previously, pedagogical practice in schools was replaced by online observations, video lessons and interactive simulations during the pandemic. Students learned to evaluate and reflect on their lesson plans using video analysis methods. This further strengthened their critical approach to the teaching process.

The conclusion reached in this area is that pedagogical practices should be organized not only in the classroom, but also in online and hybrid environments. Mentor-school collaborations and virtual observation systems should be implemented so that students gain experience in real online management (4, p.25).

Pedagogical psychology, one of the important areas of psychology, is a scientific field that studies the psychological processes occurring in the practical activities of a teacher, teacher-student relationships in the educational environment, motivation, development and consideration of individual characteristics. In this regard, pedagogical psychology in teacher training programs promotes both the acquisition of theoretical knowledge and the formation of practical pedagogical skills.

The psychological preparation of a teacher directly determines the quality of pedagogical activity, the classroom environment, student achievements, motivation and the effectiveness of the educational process. Therefore, pedagogical psychology is considered an integral part of the teacher training process.

A modern teacher is a person who creates motivation, understands the needs of students, and reveals individual potential. Psychological competencies are necessary for the fulfillment of these functions. Pedagogical psychology provides the teacher with skills such as organizing training in accordance with the age characteristics of students, applying psychological influence tools, forming motivational strategies and developing emotional intelligence.

Studies show that 30–40% of student achievement depends on the quality of the relationship with the teacher.

Each student has individual psychological characteristics: temperament, motivation type, learning style, emotional reactions are different. Pedagogical psychology allows the teacher to recognize these differences, individualize training and provide psychological support in inclusive education.

The teacher makes psychological decisions at every step, from lesson planning to assessment and behavior regulation. Pedagogical psychology explains the scientific basis of these decisions, ensuring that the teacher acts more objectively and effectively.

Modern reforms in the field of teacher training have further increased the importance of the psychological component. In university programs, pedagogical psychology is implemented in the form of theoretical lessons, practical classes, observations during pedagogical practice at school, psychological trainings and seminars.

As a result of these activities, students gain practical skills that can be applied in a real classroom setting, along with psychological knowledge.

Micro-courses, modular training, virtual mentoring programs and professional learning platforms can respond to the rapidly changing needs of teachers. OECD and UNESCO state that such models enhance networking and local-global exchange of experience.

Teacher training programs and state education policies in this area should provide teachers with appropriate devices, stable connectivity and access to learning content for the effective organization of the teaching process. These steps are necessary in terms of creating and maintaining equal opportunities in education.

Teacher training programs should include digital pedagogy, assessment, inclusive strategies and psycho-

social support modules. These modules should be supported by practical, project-based and simulated online classroom activities.

Agreements between universities and schools should serve to create online mentoring, virtual observation and feedback mechanisms. This will also serve to gain online management experience for learners.

The conducted analyses raise such a reasonable idea that courses that can support appropriate management, emotional intelligence and work-life balance should be organized within the framework of professional development. Schools should especially strengthen psychological and counseling services.

In order to improve the process, open educational resources, microcertification programs and online professional learning tools should be created for teachers at the national and regional levels. Such platforms are invaluable in ensuring the rapid sharing of best practices (5, p.12).

Teachers should be trained in formative assessment and data analysis skills, and universities should be provided with practical tools for monitoring student achievement.

The post-pandemic period has created both challenges and new opportunities for teacher training. In particular, at this stage, there were a number of difficulties, such as the weakening of teacher well-being, the continued risk of infection, and the process of adaptation to new conditions was somewhat slow due to stress and strain.

At the same time, digital educational innovations, online communities and new professional development models have emerged, which are capable of providing opportunities for more flexible implementation of teacher training.

The main condition for the path to success is a continuous learning model designed with policy-program alignment, infrastructure investments and the active participation of teachers. International reports show that successful country experiences are among those that implement these principles.

The pandemic has forced the rapid introduction of distance learning and has made it necessary to adapt teacher training to new realities. The main conclusion is that teacher training programs should no longer only systematically cover subject knowledge, but also digital pedagogy, assessment, psychosocial support and inclusive approaches (6, p.35).

Subjects such as the use of digital tools, online lesson design, and creation of multimedia resources should be constantly strengthened in teacher training programs. Digital literacy should now be considered one of the main competencies of a teacher.

Online practice models obtained during the pandemic should be systematized and standardized. This

will allow future teachers to observe different school environments and gain broader experience.

Developing students' research skills is an integral part of the educational process. Research on the effectiveness of online and hybrid teaching, the application of digital methods and the quality of the learning process can be included in the programs.

Taking into account Azerbaijan's "Digital Education Strategy (2021–2025)" and "Education Innovation Program", teacher training programs should be updated in line with national digitalization priorities. This will not only improve the quality of education in the country, but also accelerate the process of integration with international standards.

The pandemic period was marked by flexibility in teacher training, digital transformation, and the emergence of new pedagogical models. These experiences have created the basis for a more innovative, sustainable, and flexible organization of teacher training in the post-pandemic period. A synthesis of global and national experience shows that the integration of digital pedagogy, hybrid education model, and socio-emotional support into teacher training programs will be one of the main factors determining the quality of the future education system.

As we noted above, the professionalism of a teacher in the modern education system is not limited to subject knowledge alone. The 21st century school is based on a student-centered learning philosophy, and the psychological preparation of the teacher plays a decisive role in this process.

Priority areas for the state and educational institutions are: investment in infrastructure, transition to hybrid pedagogical practices, continuous micro-learning opportunities, and support for teacher well-being. Without the implementation of these mechanisms, the effectiveness of distance and hybrid education models will not be fully ensured in the near future.

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